

erance at ripening stage. Nonasail (Sel), CSR6, CSRI, M152 in that order, had tolerance at all growth stages. IR4432-28-5 and IR13426-19-2 performed well and IR9884-54-3 appeared suitable for medium saline soils. □

New IRRI publications

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Consequences of small farm mechanization

Investigaciones en arroz en los años 1980: resumen de los informes de la conferencia internacional de investigaciones en arroz del año 1982

Map series of Bangladesh: rice area planted by season, rice area planted by culture type, farm size distribution, and base map.

Field scores and survival of some promising varieties or lines in screening for tolerance for coastal salinity.

Variety or line	Plant survival at maturity (%)				Tolerance score ^a							
					Vegetative				Maturity			
	1980	1981	1982	Av	1980	1981	1982	Av	1980	1981	1982	Av
IR36	56	99	16	57	8	4	8	7	6	6	9	7
IR42	48	100	12	53	8	6	8	7	7	5	8	7
IR4432-28-5	79	98	21	66	6	4	8	6	5	4	8	6
IR9852-19-2	57	98	30	61	8	6	6	6	7	4	8	6
IR9884-54-3	73	99	19	64	7	4	7	6	6	4	8	6
IR9975-5-1	62	69	11	47	7	6	7	7	6	6	8	7
M152	34	91	74	66	8	4	3	5	7	4	4	5
M242	37	63	64	55	8	4	5	6	7	5	6	6
Nonasail (Sel)	92	87	61	80	4	4	4	4	4	4	6	4
PNL 11-2	60	9	24	31	7	4	7	6	6	7	6	6
PNL 28-23	70	61	53	61	6	6	8	6	7	6	8	7
IR10198-66-2	70	93	15	59	7	4	8	6	7	4	8	6
IR10206-29-2	59	84	22	55	8	6	8	7	7	5	8	7
IR13426-19-2	58	83	—	71	7	5	—	6	7	4	—	5
IR2307-247-2-2-3	55	99	19	58	8	4	8	6	6	5	8	6
IR2863-35-3-3	79	96	5	60	6	6	9	7	5	5	9	6
Pokkali	7	60	4	24	8	9	9	8	6	7	8	7
M-1-48	59	2	—	30	8	9	—	9	9	9	—	9
CSRI		97	37	67	—	4	6	5	—	3	5	4

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1-9: 1 = growth and tillering nearly normal; 9 = almost all plants dead or dying.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Performance of some promising varieties in floating-rice areas of Cuu Long Delta

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Deepwater rice is grown on about 0.5 million ha on the Cuu Long (Mekong) Delta. Most is grown in An Giang, Dong Thap, Kien Giang, Hau Giang, and Long An Provinces. There is little information on agronomic characteristics and yield of popular local varieties.

We compared local varieties Nang Tay Dum, Nang Tay Lon, Nang Chet Cut, Ba Bong, Sa Mo Chum, Cu La, and introduced varieties Leb Mue Nahng 111, BKNFR76031-1-13-1, BKNFR76047-4-3-1, and RD19 at An Giang and Hau Giang (see table).

In Jun 1982 1-month-old seedlings were transplanted in 25- × 25-cm spacing at 1 seedling/hill. Maximum water depth

Grain yield and plant characters of some photoperiod-sensitive rices in floating-rice areas of Cuu Long (Mekong) Delta, S. R. Vietnam, 1982.

Variety	Date of heading	Height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Field grains/panicle	Unfilled grains %	1000-grain weight (g)	Yield ^d (t/ha)	
Local				<i>An Giang</i>				
Ba Bong	07 Dec	260	89	146	12.3	32.2	3.0	def
Cu La	20 Nov	247	108	151	16.3	23.9	3.3	cd
Nang Chet Cut	17 Nov	250	92	151	18.2	24.8	2.9	ef
Nang Tay Dum	23 Nov	254	89	195	18.4	22.8	3.6	a
Nang Tay Lon	23 Nov	255	83	133	15.9	29.7	3.6	ab
Sa Mo Chum	25 Nov	237	103	165	14.3	22.5	3.4	abc
<i>Introduced^b</i>								
BKNFR76031-1-13-1	23 Nov	228	92	82	30.9	34.4	2.5	g
BKNFR76047-4-3-1	01 Dec	210	69	98	27.9	28.7	2.2	g
Leb Mue Nahng 111	22 Nov	255	88	116	22.7	31.8	3.0	def
RD19	05 Dec	208	117	62	25.3	30.7	3.1	cde
Local				<i>Hau Giang</i>				
Ba Bong	01 Dec	212	69	121	18.0	33.3	3.7	a
Cu La	19 Nov	231	88	84	30.7	24.3	2.5	b
Nang Chet Cut	15 Nov	248	75	99	20.0	24.6	2.6	b
Nang Tay Dum	30 Nov	244	65	158	20.5	23.3	2.7	b
Nang Tay Lon	20 Nov	258	71	102	20.2	28.3	2.5	b
<i>Introduced^b</i>								
BKNFR76031-1-13-1	21 Nov	245	76	96	24.1	34.9	2.5	b
Leb Mue Nahng 111	20 Nov	256	62	103	23.9	32.0	2.4	b
Pin Gaew 56	15 Dec	298	84	127	19.2	30.8	3.4	a

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^bFrom Thailand.

was 161 cm at An Giang and 146 cm at Hau Giang in late Oct (see figure).

At An Giang, Nang Tay Dum yielded highest (3.6 t/ha) and was significantly superior to Nang Tay Lon and Sa Mo Chum. It also had the highest number of filled panicles. Nang Tay Lon had highest grain weight and Sa Mo Chum had more panicles/m². Ba Bong was superior at Hau Giang. Soil type may have caused differences in varietal performance in the two locations. Hau Giang has slightly acid sulfate soil and An Giang has normal alluvial soil.

Introduced varieties had a higher percentage of unfilled grains than local varieties, except Pin Gaew 56, which had a large number of filled grains/panicle and high grain weight (see table).

BKNFR76031-1-1-13-1, BKNFR76047-4-3-1, and RD19 had less adaptability in An Giang, a typical floating rice area, because they have lower elongation ability and can be damaged by deep flooding.

Leb Mue Nahng 111 and Pin Gaew 56 had elongation ability similar to that of local varieties. Ba Bong and Pin Gaew 56 were

late maturing and had longer plants and good kneeing ability, making them suitable for deep water.

Elongation rate of some deepwater rices of Bihar, India

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Deepwater rices are characterized by rapid elongation of stem, sheath, and leaf blade when water rises. If water rises gradually, they keep their leaves above the surface. Elongation rate of many local deepwater cultivars grown in Bihar has not been established. We recorded daily elongation of local varieties Janaki (64-117), BR14, Pichar, Barogar, Desaria,

Malida, and 62-68.

Forty-day-old potted seedlings were submerged in a 1-m-deep water tank. Water level was adjusted daily, and height was measured on 4 consecutive days.

Daily elongation rate varied. Maximum daily elongation was 26 cm for Desaria, 25 cm for Barogar, 18 cm for Pichar, 13 cm for Janaki (64-117), 12 cm for BR14 and for 62-68, and 7 cm for Malida. The time of greatest elongation also varied. Desaria, Barogar, and 62-68 had greatest elongation on day 1; Pichar, Malida, and BR14 on day 4; and Janaki (64-117) on day 3 (see table).

Barogar and Desaria, both floating rices, elongated fastest, and had greatest day 1 elongation, which is desirable.

Average daily elongation of local deepwater rice in Bihar, India.

Variety	Av daily elongation (cm)							
	Day 1		Day 2		Day 3		Day 4	
	Av	Range	Av	Range	Av	Range	Av	Range
Janaki (64-117)	2	0.2-5.4	5	0.7-6.5	5	1.0-12.7	3	0.5-10.8
Pichar	4	1.2-8.2	2	0.3-3.8	4	0.5-13.3	14	1.5-18.0
Barogar	16	8.0-25.0	8	4.0-17.0	8	2.0-17.0	8	2.0-17.2
Desaria	9	2.0-14.0	6	1.4-10.4	14	5.1-26.1	5	1.0-13.0
Malida	1	0.2-3.5	3	1.6-5.0	3	1.0-4.5	6	3.0-7.0
62-68	7	4.5-10.0	8	5.5-12.0	4	1.0-6.2	2	0.5-6.1
BR14	7	0.5-7.0	5	0.5-10.0	4	0.5-10.3	9	5.0-11.7

Field Problems of Tropical Rice

Field Problems of Tropical Rice, revised 1983, provides simple, easy-to-read information to help rice workers identify major insects, diseases, weeds, and soil problems. More than 150 color photographs illustrate the pocket-sized field guide. The first edition of *Field Problems* was copublished in 11 non-English languages and more than 200,000 copies were distributed by local publishers, research institutes, and national and international agricultural research centers. For information about purchase and/or translation-copublication rights, please write: IRRI, Communication and Publications Dept., Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

